

HISTORICAL PREREQUISITES FOR THE CREATION OF SOS CHILDREN'S NEIGHBORHOODS

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history of the creation of SOS Children's neighborhoods, its definition, structure, and the activities that children's neighborhoods are currently doing on a global scale, as well as the research conducted by scientists on this topic.

Keywords: SOS, orphans and neglected children, German Gmayner, Imst, youth houses

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"All the children of the world are our children."

(G.Gmayner)

Introduction

SOS Children's villages are the world's largest non-governmental organization dedicated to supporting children left without parental care and families at risk. Since 1949, the organization has been working to ensure that children grow up in a loving family environment and comply with their rights. SOS Children's villages work in 136 countries and territories, helping children, youth and families, providing quality care, empowering families and communities, and helping to ensure children's rights beradi. So over the past 70 years, SOS Children's villages have supported 4 million children through alternative care and family strengthening. SOS Children's villages work on the basis of innovative and effective cooperation with donors, communities, governments and other organizations.

SOS Children's villages 2030 strategy is directly related to sustainability goals and helps them achieve them in important areas such as poverty, inequality, education, health, social and child protection and decent work.¹⁵

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

SOS-Children's neighborhoods is a non-profit organization established for the purpose of ensuring the well-being of children, protecting their interests and rights,

¹⁵ sos-kids.uz

and meeting their needs. Children and young people who are left without parental care or are under the threat of social orphanhood, as well as families who find themselves in a difficult life situation, are the focus of the organization's activities. Within the framework of the organization's programs, children and families have integrated, consistent and continuous services aimed at creating a family environment for children and young people left without parental care, strengthening families in difficult life situations and reducing the risk of social orphanhood.

Born into a large family of farmers in Vorarlberg (today Austria), Gmeiner was a talented child and won a scholarship to study at a grammar school. Her mother died when she was still young, and her older sister Elsa took care of the youngest of the children.

Having experienced the horrors of war as a soldier in Russia , the children lost their parents in the war and were completely in danger unattended. Since the SOS Children's village was still in this difficult period, funds were missing, it had to be started very small. What a success that has not yet been here in the following years and decades, in which SOS Children's villages grew rapidly across Austria, and that could spread internationally after the end of the war, he faced suffering and suffering as a worker for the welfare of many orphaned and neglected children. He felt that after World War II, children were obliged to grow up without their own home, that something had to be done to help them in the belief that help would never be effective, and against this background set out to implement his idea of setting up SOS Children's villages.

With only 600 Austrian schilling (about US \$ 40) in his pocket, Herman Gmeiner founded the SOS Children's Village Association, SOCIETAS SOCIALIS, in 1949, with the help of his fellow students, and in the same year the foundation was laid for the first SOS Children's village in Imst, Austria. Tyrol. His work with children and the development of the SOS Children's village organization made Herman Gmayer so busy that, as a result, he decided to stop the medical course.

In the following decades, his life was closely linked to his commitment to the concept of child care based on the four pillars of the mother, house, brothers and sisters and the village. Given his special attention to the need to help abandoned children, his other biography resembles the history of SOS Children's villages. He served as village director at Imst, later organizing the construction of SOS Children's villages in Austria and helping to establish SOS Children's villages in many other European countries.¹⁶

Currently, Imst has 15 family homes, some outbuildings, and a community center. They house an office, a church and a large hall. SOS will also look after the

¹⁶ Hermann Gmeiner: impressions, thoughts, confessions, 1989, pp. 5-33

surrounding children in kindergarten. Older children attend local schools in Imst boradilar. Ba Zi teenagers live in the SOS Youth Institution in Telfs. The SOS Children's neighborhood also has a retirement mother's house, where retired SOS mothers retire without interruption from life in the SOS Children's neighborhood.¹⁷

In 1960, SOS-Kinderdorf International was founded in Strasbourg as an umbrella organization for SOS Children's villages, with Hermann Gmeiner as the first president. In subsequent years, the activities of SOS Children's villages spread beyond Europe. The sensational "rice grain" campaign raised enough funds to build the first non-European SOS Children's village to be built in Tegu, Korea in 1963, and later SOS Children's villages on the American and African continents.

By 1985, the result of Hermann Gmeiner's work was a total of 233 SOS Children's villages in 85 countries. For his services to orphans and abandoned children, he was awarded many, including: the Nobel Peace Prize and was repeatedly nominated for this award. However, he always suffered to emphasize that the goal of providing abandoned children with a permanent home was made thanks to the support of millions of people who could achieve it, and this is still valid.

Hermann Gmeiner, who thought about the fate of orphans and neglected children and connected his life with them, died in Innsbruck in 1986. He was buried in the SOS Children's village Imst.

In 2017, more than 85,000 children and young people were raised in 572 SOS Children's villages and more than 700 SOS Youth Institutions. Another 3.8 million children and adults received services under other programs. SOS Children's villages today operate in 135 countries and territories. 438 SOS Children's villages and 346 SOS youth institutions provide over 60,000 children and young people with a new home.

More than 131,000 children and young people participate in SOS kindergartens, SOS Hermann Gmeiner schools and SOS vocational education centers. 397,000 people are being served by SOS medical centers and 115,000 by SOS social centers. SOS Children's villages also help in crisis and disaster situations through emergency assistance programs. The emergency medical clinic in Mogadishu (which provides a program with 260,000 examinations and treatments per year) is one of the huge examples of a long-term care program.

The association "SOS Children's neighborhoods of Uzbekistan" is a non-profit organization founded in 1997 in order to ensure the well-being of children, protect their interests and rights and meet their needs. Children and young people who are left without parental care or are under the threat of social orphanhood, as well as

¹⁷ Hermann Gmeiner: special upbringing to Die Soskinderd page 18

families who find themselves in a difficult life situation, are the focus of the organization's activities.

Within the framework of the association's programs, children and families will receive complex, consistent and uninterrupted services aimed at creating a family environment for children and young people left without parental care, strengthening families in difficult life situations and reducing the risk of social orphanhood. All services are provided within the framework of the following structures: family guardianship, guardianship over young people, structures for strengthening the family.

Four important principles of association:

1. Every child has a caring father or mother
2. Family ties develop in a taste way
3. Each family creates its own home
4. SOS-the family is part of society

Important functions of the association:

1. Creating favorable conditions for the physical, intellectual and spiritual development of children left without parental care, as well as children whose families have fallen into difficult life conditions, providing them with social and legal support.

2. Raising children deprived of parental care, taking into account the traditional and national principles of Uzbekistan.

3. The organization of social centers and the support of families who have fallen into difficult life conditions through the provision of psihological and legal support.

4. Active involvement of state, public and private structures in the activities of the Association, increasing public awareness on issues of child custody and exchange of experience on them.

The association "SOS Children's neighborhoods Uzbekistan" is a member of the international organization "SOS Children's neighborhoods". It carries out its activities within the framework of the agreement concluded between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the international organization "SOS Children's neighborhoods".

SOS Children's villages over the years:

The 1949 SOS Children's villages were founded in Austria by Hermann Gmayner and the first SOS Children's village is located in Imst

1955-the first SOS Youth Institution was founded in Innsbruck, Austria.SOS Children's villages associations, founded in France, Germany and Italy.

1960s SOS Children's Villages International was established as an umbrella organization for all SOS Children's village associations, SOS Children's villages begin operations in Latin America starting in Uruguay.

1963 the first SOS Children's villages in Asia were established in South Korea and India.

1970-the first African SOS Children's village was built in Côte d'Ivoire; the first programs began in Ghana and Sierra Leone.

1985 Helmut Kutin took the post of President of the international organization SOS Children's villages after Hermann Gmayner.

On April 26, 1986, Hermann Gmayner, who founded about 230 SOS Children's villages around the world, died. Both SOS Children's villages and Hermann Gmayner himself were repeatedly nominated for the Nobel Peace Prize.

In 1991, SOS Children's villages were reopened in Czechoslovakia. In Poland and the Soviet Union, the first SOS Children's villages were launched. SOS Children's village programs started in Bulgaria and Romania. The first SOS Children's village was established in the USA .

The 1995 SOS Children's Village International Organization held UN status and became the NTT in the United Nations Economic and Social Council as a consultant.

2002 SOS Children's Village International Organization for Outstanding Contribution to the relief of human suffering Conrad N. Hilton receives the Humanitarian Award.

2003 SOS Children's neighborhood family consolidation programs were established.

Following the 2005 Asian tsunami, SOS Children's villages will carry out the largest emergency relief and reconstruction program in the organization's history in India, Sri Lanka, Indonesia and Thailand.

The 2007 SOS Children's villages help victims of the natural disaster in Bolivia, Indonesia, Peru and Uruguay, as well as those displaced in the areas of Sudan, Chad and Somalia that suffered from the crisis. SOS family strengthening programs currently cover 80,000 children.

In 2009, the 500th SOS Children's neighborhood was opened and the organization turned 60 years old. SOS Children's neighborhoods have made important contributions to the instruction on alternative child care officially approved by the UN General Assembly.

After the devastating 2010 Haiti earthquake, more than 500 unaccompanied children were given a temporary home in SOS Children's villages in Santo and Kap Haiti. Thousands of Haitian children's SOS Children's villages are fed through an emergency feeding dastardly.

In June 2012, International SOS Children's villages held its 19th General Assembly and Siddharta elected Kaul as president instead of Helmut Kutin.

2013 more than 82,000 children and young people are raised and cared for in 554 SOS Children's villages and more than 600 youth institutions around the world. Another 328 thousand children and adults are using the strengthening of the SOS Family.

The SOS Children's village associations of 11 countries of 2014 share advanced experience in creating family-friendly and family-like care programs in an urban environment with community know-how integration. SOS Children's villages Madagascar was awarded the UNESCO-Hamdani award for teacher training, and the international football star Vincent Kompany became the International Ambassador.

In response to the 2015 refugee crisis, SOS Children's villages provide assistance to refugees, internally displaced families and unaccompanied children in at least 12 countries.

In June 2016, Siddharta was re-elected president at the 20th General Assembly of the Kaul SOS Children's Villages International Organization, in September SOS Children's villages will receive the Queen of Asturias Award for Concord from the Spanish royal family.

2017 SOS Children's villages will launch a new global partnership YouthCan. In Johannesburg, South Africa, YouthCan helps young people to expand their opportunities for independent life and successful management of the transition to the labor market.

The 2018 merger forces, the six most child-oriented non-yitic NGOs, including the SOS Children's village Alliance, will take the children's initiative to change cultural and social relations to end child abuse.

The 2019 SOS Children's villages relativize its 70th anniversary and publish its "70 years of Impact" Report.

In December 2020, SOS Children's villages Ingrid Maria Yakhansen announces that she has been appointed chief director since January 2021.

2021 independent non-profit organization "Child Safety conservation" will publish an independent review on the protection of children in SOS Children's villages "for the elimination of a child protection malfunction. This review, compiled by the international Senate of SOS Children's villages, provides combined conclusions and recommendations with the aim of contributing to the improvement of protective practices.

2022 SOS Children's villages in Ukraine are mobilizing to support thousands of children affected by war. Hundreds of Ukrainian children are placed in foster

care and public institutions, as well as single parent families, SOS Children's villages throughout Europe.¹⁸

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that SOS Children's villages are an independent, non-governmental, non-profit International Development Organization. The organization provides humanitarian and development assistance to needy children, protecting their interests and rights around the world. SOS Children's villages provide alternative families to children left without parental care. Different children of different ages and backgrounds live with their parents in a full-time home, usually with a woman who serves as the parents of the children. There are 6 to 15 homes in SOS Village. In addition to villages, the organization also produces all programs and opportunities to support socially disadvantaged families through privileged kindergartens, primary and secondary schools, youth institutions and social and medical centers, and emergency response operations.

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